

A Practical Approach to Bearing Fault Detection using Pretrained ResNet18

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Abstract—Bearing fault classification is essential for predictive maintenance, yet it is often hindered by limited labeled data and variable real-world conditions. This study investigates the use of a ResNet18 model pretrained on ImageNet and fine-tuned on time-frequency representations of vibration signals for fault classification. Utilizing the Paderborn dataset, which includes data under varying operational conditions, vibration signals were processed using envelope spectrum analysis to capture time-frequency characteristics. The model was evaluated on both laboratory and real-world datasets. The experimental results demonstrate that the fine-tuned ResNet18 model achieved robust performance, particularly when evaluated on real-world vibration data. The model exhibited rapid convergence during training and attained a high validation accuracy of 95.96%, highlighting its effectiveness and practical applicability for bearing fault classification tasks. These findings highlight the model's potential for efficient and accurate fault detection in industrial environments, even with limited annotated data.

Keywords—Bearing fault, ResNet18, Paderborn.

I. INTRODUCTION AND RELATED WORK

Accurate and reliable diagnostics of rotating machinery remain a critical challenge in various industrial applications. These machines are vital assets, and their failure or downtime often results in significant economic losses. Among their components, bearings are consistently identified as the most failure-prone elements in rotating electrical machines, as highlighted in multiple industrial surveys and reviews [1-2]. Consequently, bearing fault diagnosis and prognosis have become key areas of research, driving advancements in signal processing and automated fault detection techniques [3-4].

One major research trend is the use of machine learning for automatic bearing fault detection. This direction has gained momentum with the emergence of open-source datasets, such as those from Case Western Reserve University (CWRU) [5] and Paderborn University (PU) [6], which provide rich resources for algorithm development and benchmarking. Machine learning approaches to bearing fault diagnosis can be categorized in several ways. Beyond the conventional distinction between supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning, these methods are also classified as either shallow or deep, depending on their feature extraction strategies [7]. Shallow learning methods often rely

on manual feature engineering, whereas deep learning models automatically learn relevant patterns directly from raw data, eliminating the need for manual intervention.

Deep learning has notably transformed the field, with techniques such as autoencoders, deep belief networks, recurrent neural networks, generative adversarial networks, and, most prominently, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [9]. CNNs, in particular, have shown great promise in fault diagnosis, largely due to their success in image classification and their strong capabilities in data mining and adaptive feature learning [10]. Their application to rotating machinery diagnostics has been explored in various studies [11].

This work contributes to the field of predictive maintenance by evaluating the performance of a ResNet18 model pretrained on ImageNet, fine-tuned on time-frequency representations of vibration signals. The study demonstrates how pretrained convolutional neural networks can effectively classify bearing faults with high accuracy, even under variable real-world conditions. The results highlight the model's ability to generalize well with limited annotated data, offering a practical solution for industrial fault diagnosis.

II. METHODOLOGY

The following methodology is structured into three main parts, reflecting the key phases of the proposed approach. First, we describe the signal transformation techniques applied to the raw vibration data in order to generate suitable time-frequency representations. Second, we present an overview of the ResNet18 architecture and explain how it was adapted for the bearing fault classification task. Finally, we outline the complete transfer learning pipeline, detailing the training procedure. Together, these three steps form the foundation of our proposed approach to bearing fault classification using deep learning.

A. Signal Transformation

Faults in rolling element bearings often originate on the surfaces in direct contact with the rolling elements, specifically the Inner Race, Outer Race, or the rolling elements themselves, which are typically spherical in radially loaded bearings. These defects may be either localized or distributed along the circumferential surfaces of the bearing

races, depending on the nature and progression of the damage. During operation, the interaction between rolling elements and defective surfaces generates mechanical shocks that propagate through the bearing structure in the form of vibration. The vibration characteristics differ depending on whether the fault is localized or distributed. Localized defects, such as spalls or pits, typically result in vibration signals exhibiting clear periodicity. This periodic nature arises from the regular intervals at which the rolling elements strike the defect, a pattern that is inherently linked to the geometry of the bearing and its rotational speed. In contrast, distributed defects produce more diffuse vibration responses, often lacking a clearly defined periodic structure due to the continuous nature of the damage. The characteristic frequencies associated with localized bearing faults depend on bearing geometry and rotational speed, and are analytically defined in [12]. The time-domain vibration signals are transformed into physically meaningful time-frequency maps by utilizing the methodology proposed in [12]. The present approach extends classical envelope spectrum analysis into the time-frequency domain, enabling the simultaneous tracking of amplitude and frequency variations for improved detection.

Figure 1 and Figure 2 illustrate two distinct signals corresponding to Inner Race and Outer Race defects, respectively, each represented in terms of amplitude and frequency to highlight the characteristic differences in their spectral content.

Figure 1. Signals corresponding to Inner Race defects.

The time-frequency representation of such images indicates different signatures for different defects, which are utilized to fine-tune and validate the proposed network.

Figure 2. Signals corresponding to Outer Race defects.

B. ResNet18 Description and Adaptation

ResNet-18 is a widely used convolutional neural network architecture that is part of the ResNet (Residual Network) family which introduced the concept of residual learning to address the vanishing gradient problem in deep neural networks. ResNet-18 is one of the smaller variants in the ResNet series, with 18 layers, other variants being ResNet-50, ResNet-101, and ResNet-152. ResNet-18 consists of 18 layers, which includes convolutional layers, batch normalization layers, and fully connected layers. Specifically, it has 8 residual blocks, each containing two convolutional layers. The hallmark of ResNet architectures is the use of skip connections (or shortcut connections) in residual blocks. These connections bypass one or more layers, allowing the network to learn residual mappings instead of directly learning the desired output. This mitigates the degradation problem in very deep networks. With approximately 11.7 million learnable parameters and occupying around 43 MB in memory, ResNet-18 is considered relatively lightweight, making it well-suited for applications where computational efficiency and memory constraints are critical.

ImageNet plays a pivotal role in the development and application of pretrained models in computer vision. Pretrained models refer to neural networks that have been trained on large-scale datasets, such as ImageNet, and whose learned parameters (weights and biases) can be reused for other tasks. ImageNet, with its vast collection of over 14 million labeled images spanning thousands of categories,

serves as an ideal dataset for pretraining due to its diversity and scale. ResNet-18, like many other convolutional neural network architectures, is commonly pretrained on ImageNet. During pretraining, the model learns to extract hierarchical features from images, starting with low-level features such as edges and textures and progressing to high-level features like shapes and object parts. These learned features are generalizable and can be transferred to a wide range of computer vision tasks, including object detection, image segmentation, and fine-grained classification.

Using pretrained ResNet-18 models significantly reduces the computational cost and time required for training on smaller datasets. Instead of training a model from scratch, researchers and practitioners can initialize their networks with the pretrained weights from ImageNet and fine-tune the model on their specific dataset. This process not only accelerates training but also improves performance, especially when the target dataset is limited in size or lacks diversity.

C. Transfer Learning Pipeline

The transfer learning process begins with leveraging a pretrained ResNet-18 network, originally trained on the ImageNet 1K dataset. ImageNet's 1,000-class classification layer is replaced with a new output layer tailored to the specific requirements of the bearing fault detection problem. This new layer is designed to predict three distinct classes: Healthy, Inner Race Fault, and Outer Race Fault.

The transfer learning pipeline is shown in Figure 3 and is structured in two stages: the first involves adapting the pretrained model using laboratory data under controlled conditions, while the second stage consists of fine-tuning the model on a smaller portion of real-world data to enhance generalization and performance in practical scenarios.

Figure 3. Transfer learning pipeline.

Stage 1: Adapting to Lab Data

The modified ResNet-18 network is first trained on a Lab dataset, which consists of data generated from bearings with artificially induced damages. This dataset provides labeled examples for the three fault categories, enabling the network to adapt its feature extraction capabilities to the bearing fault detection domain. During this stage, the pretrained weights from ImageNet serve as a strong initialization, allowing the network to focus on learning domain-specific patterns while retaining general visual features learned during pretraining.

Stage 2: Fine-Tuning with Real-World Data

To ensure the model performs effectively in real-world scenarios, a second fine-tuning step is introduced. In this step, a small subset of real-world data, gathered from life-accelerated tests, is used to refine the network further. This real-world data captures the nuances and variability inherent in actual bearing setups, which may differ from the controlled conditions of the lab dataset. Fine-tuning on this data helps bridge the gap between simulated and real-world environments, enhancing the model's robustness and reliability.

Once the network is fine-tuned in Stage 1, it is packaged and shipped to end users. In practice, end users are encouraged

to perform an additional round of fine-tuning using data collected from their specific setups. This step ensures the model adapts to the unique characteristics of each deployment environment, such as variations in operating conditions, equipment configurations, or sensor placements. By enabling end users to customize the model further, the pipeline maximizes its applicability and accuracy in diverse real-world scenarios.

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Following the transfer learning pipeline described above, the network successfully classifies the remaining real-world scenarios, achieving an accuracy of 95.96% and an F1 score of 0.9553. Analysis of the confusion matrix, see Figure 4, reveals that all Inner Race defect samples were classified correctly.

Figure 4. The confusion matrix, where IR is Inner Race and OR is Outer Race.

However, some Outer Race samples were occasionally misclassified as Inner Race or Healthy, and some Healthy samples were also misclassified as Inner Race. Overall, the network exhibits a slight bias towards classifying samples as having an Inner Race defect.

It is important to note that the real-world data utilized in the second stage comprised 25% of the total dataset, with the remaining 75% reserved for validation of the final model. Regarding the Healthy class data—which is considered both artificial and real simultaneously—10% was used in the first stage and another 10% in the second stage, leaving 80% for validation purposes. The model was trained using the Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 and a momentum parameter set to 0.9.

The application of a pretrained ResNet18 model enhances the training process by leveraging its robust and well-established feature extraction capabilities. This approach offers multiple advantages, including ease of implementation and efficient fine-tuning, due to the extensive prior training on large-scale datasets such as ImageNet, which contains 1,000 classes. The residual architecture of ResNet18 facilitates effective learning of deep hierarchical features, contributing to strong generalization performance even when training data is limited. These characteristics make ResNet18 a reliable and effective solution for bearing fault classification in industrial environments.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of using a pretrained ResNet18 model, fine-tuned on time-frequency representations of vibration signals, for bearing fault classification. The model was evaluated on two distinct datasets: one consisting of controlled laboratory data and another comprising a subset of real-world operational data. By replacing the final fully connected layer to match the number of fault classes, the ResNet18 architecture was successfully adapted to the specific fault diagnosis task. The results highlight the practical value of employing pretrained convolutional neural networks in industrial scenarios where labeled data is often scarce. The model achieved high accuracy and fast convergence across both datasets, demonstrating strong generalization capabilities, robustness to variable conditions, and a minimal computational footprint. These attributes make pretrained models like ResNet18 particularly suitable for deployment in predictive maintenance and real-world industrial environments.

Future work will focus on exploring lightweight CNN architectures that offer further reductions in computational and memory requirements, enabling real-time inference on edge devices within IoT-based monitoring systems. Additionally, integrating explainable AI methods is planned to enhance model transparency and provide interpretable insights into classification decisions. Such techniques could support better understanding of the learned features and guide future model improvements through more targeted data and architectural adjustments.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Nandi, S., Toliyat, H. A., & Li, X. (2005). Condition monitoring and fault diagnosis of electrical motors—A review. *IEEE transactions on energy conversion*, 20(4), 719-729.
- [2] Albrecht, P. F., Appiarius, J. C., McCoy, R. M., Owen, E. L., & Sharma, D. K. (1986). Assessment of the reliability of motors in utility applications-Updated. *IEEE Transactions on Energy conversion*, (1), 39-46.
- [3] Rai, A., & Upadhyay, S. H. (2016). A review on signal processing techniques utilized in the fault diagnosis of rolling element bearings. *Tribology International*, 96, 289-306.
- [4] Kannan, V., Zhang, T., & Li, H. (2024). A review of the intelligent condition monitoring of rolling element bearings. *Machines*, 12(7), 484.
- [5] <https://engineering.case.edu/bearingdatacenter/normal-baseline-data>
- [6] Lessmeier, C., Kimotho, J. K., Zimmer, D., & Sestro, W. (2016, July). Condition monitoring of bearing damage in electromechanical drive systems by using motor current signals of electric motors: A benchmark data set for data-driven classification. In *PHM society European conference* (Vol. 3, No. 1).
- [7] Hamadache, M., Jung, J. H., Park, J., & Youn, B. D. (2019). A comprehensive review of artificial intelligence-based approaches for rolling element bearing PHM: Shallow and deep learning. *JMST Advances*, 1, 125-151.
- [8] Zhang, S., Zhang, S., Wang, B., & Habetler, T. G. (2020). Deep learning algorithms for bearing fault diagnostics—A comprehensive review. *IEEE access*, 8, 29857-29881.
- [9] Li, X., Ma, Z., Yuan, Z., Mu, T., Du, G., Liang, Y., & Liu, J. (2024). A review on convolutional neural network in rolling bearing fault diagnosis. *Measurement Science and Technology*.
- [10] Shao, H., Xia, M., Han, G., Zhang, Y., & Wan, J. (2020). Intelligent fault diagnosis of rotor-bearing system under varying working conditions with modified transfer convolutional neural network and thermal images. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, 17(5), 3488-3496.
- [11] Wang, Z., Han, G., Liu, L., Wang, F., & Zhu, Y. (2025). A Globally Interpretable Convolutional Neural Network Combining Bearing Semantics for Bearing Fault Diagnosis. *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*.
- [12] Ruiz-Sarrio, J. E., Antonino-Daviu, J. A., & Martis, C. (2024). Localized Bearing Fault Analysis for Different Induction Machine Start-Up Modes via Vibration Time-Frequency Envelope Spectrum. *Sensors*, 24(21), 6935.